

Critical Review and Analysis of *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions
According to Paul* by Roland Allen and Its Modern Implications

Sean Shetler
CHRI-6314-C01: Missions and Evangelism
Dr. Steven Edworthy

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I. Introduction

A. Overview of the Book

Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul (Updated Edition) by Roland Allen (c. 1868 – 1947 AD) was first published in 1912, and second printing in 1927, with an updated edition released in 2017. The book begins with the author's preface and introduction, and concludes with an epilogue and an "About the Author" section. The body of the book is divided into five parts. Part I includes three sections: Strategic Points, Class, and Moral and Social Condition. Part II also contains three sections: Miracles, Finance, and The Substance of Paul's Preaching. Part III is divided into two parts: The Teaching and the Training of Candidates for Membership and Ministry. Part IV consists of two sections: Authority and Discipline, and Unity. Finally, Part V contains three sections: Principles and Spirit, Application, and A Present-Day Contrast¹.

B. Second Printing of the Book in 1927

Fifteen years after its initial publication, the second edition of *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul* was released in 1927, primarily to provide a more affordable version of the work. In the years following the first edition, the study of Paul's missionary methods has profoundly influenced modern approaches to missions. Roland Allen asserts that a deeper understanding of Paul's practices offers valuable solutions to many contemporary missionary challenges.

Central to Roland Allen's argument is his belief that Paul's churches were genuinely indigenous, with the local church at the heart of his strategy, contrasting with the broader "national" church models common in today's missions. Allen underscores that Paul's unwavering trust in the Holy Spirit's indwelling presence in new believers allowed him to establish churches with full authority—a trust in the Spirit that Allen argues is often missing in contemporary missions. Modern missionaries, he contends, tend to place more faith in the Holy Spirit's work within themselves rather than in the Spirit's transformative power within their converts, a shift that impedes the growth of truly indigenous churches².

C. Two Primary Objections to the Books Initial Release

Roland Allen reflects on the early reviews of his book, noting that while critics largely accepted his description of apostolic practice, they raised two primary objections: (1) the cultural and contextual differences between Paul's time and today's missions make the direct application of his methods more difficult, and (2) Paul's reliance on synagogue converts to safeguard the churches from heresy is no longer possible in the same way. These critiques, Allen acknowledges, highlight the challenges missionaries face today but also reinforce the continuing relevance of Paul's example in navigating those challenges.

¹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), ix.

² Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), ix-x.

Allen addresses two main criticisms regarding the application of apostolic methods in contemporary missions. To the first criticism, which suggests that the cultural gap between the early church and modern missionary contexts is too wide to apply Paul's methods, Allen responds in his book *Education Principles and Missionary Methods*. He argues that the greater the cultural divide, the more valuable the apostolic approach becomes. While the full argument is too extensive to summarize here, Allen believes that the differences in culture only emphasize the need for a deeper understanding and application of Paul's methods³.

D. Response to the Second Round of Criticism

In response to the second criticism, which questions whether Paul's methods could still be effective given the perceived moral and doctrinal challenges in today's missionary settings, Roland Allen offers several points (six to be exact) to support his claim: (1) The dangers we fear today—such as moral decline or the confusion of Christian doctrine by external influences like pagan philosophy—were no less prevalent in Paul's time. (2) The early and significant division between the synagogue and the Christian church led to the establishment of churches that were not “off-shoots” of local synagogues. Despite this, the apostolic practice was preserved. (3) In cities like Corinth, Galatia, and Ephesus, the presence of Jews and proselytes did not prevent doctrinal dangers from emerging. When Paul relied on them, they failed to prevent these issues. (4) To argue that Mosaic Law provides a better foundation for Christian morality and theology than the teachings of Christ and the Holy Spirit would be flawed. (5) Paul's faith in Christ and the Holy Spirit compelled him to act as he did under any circumstances, demonstrating that he did not rely on pagan philosophy or Mosaic teachings to establish his converts. (6) If we told people in regions like China or India that they were morally and intellectually inferior to the Jews and proselytes of Paul's day, they would be deeply offended. The argument should not be restricted to any specific geographical area; the same apostolic methods should be applied universally⁴.

After reflecting on the insights and feedback gained over the past fifteen years, Allen decided not to make substantial changes to the book but instead made only minimal updates. He believed the book's message was powerful enough that it did not require a major revision. Allen expands on these ideas in a companion volume, *The Spontaneous Expansion of the Church and the Causes Which Hinder It*, where he delves into the extraordinary growth of apostolic churches and examines the barriers that prevent similar progress today. For readers interested in exploring missionary methods further, Allen suggests turning to this companion work⁵.

³ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), x-xi.

⁴ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xi.

⁵ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), x-xiii; Romans 15:19-20: “(19 by the power of signs and wonders, by the power of the Spirit of God—so that from Jerusalem and all the way around to Illyricum I have fulfilled the ministry of the gospel of Christ; (20 and thus I make it my ambition to preach the gospel, not where Christ has already been named, lest I build on someone else's foundation.” The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Romans 15:19-20).

II. Review of the First-Half of Missionary Methods

A. Paul's Teachings and Organizational Strategies: Enduring Through the Ages

Roland Allen calls attention to the remarkable success of the Apostle Paul's missionary efforts in a short span of just over a decade. By 57 AD, Paul had established churches in four major provinces of the Roman Empire: Galatia, Macedonia, Achaia, and Asia—regions where no Christian communities had existed before 47 AD. What stands out is that by the time he could plan his missions to the far west, Paul did so with confidence that the churches he had founded would continue to thrive in his absence. Allen emphasizes that Paul's work in these provinces should be viewed as a unified and completed effort. While Paul was not without help, he alone can be credited with the establishment of these churches (Romans 15:19-20)⁶.

His ministry was not just a temporary measure but one that laid solid *foundations*, ensuring that the churches were self-sustaining. The author of Acts of the Apostles, Allen argues, presents Paul's mission as fully accomplished when he left these churches. Despite any challenges or failures that might have arisen later, the apostle's teachings and organizational efforts were robust enough to endure beyond his direct involvement. Allen suggests that Paul's departure from these churches was not a sign of neglect, but rather a testament to the completeness of his work⁷.

B. Rapid Growth and Revolutionary Missionary Methods

Allen puts forth a strikingly bold claim about the Apostle Paul's extraordinary success in establishing churches throughout the Roman Empire. The rapid and secure founding of these churches, in Allen's assessment, is nothing short of remarkable, particularly when compared to the missionary efforts of later centuries. For those familiar with the struggles, setbacks, and prolonged efforts of modern missions, Paul's accomplishments might seem almost unbelievable (2 Corinthians 4:8-9)⁸. Allen observes that while many later missionaries have converted more

⁶ Romans 15:19–20 states: “(19) By the power of signs and wonders, by the power of the Spirit of God, (b) so that from Jerusalem and as far around as Illyricum I have fully proclaimed the good news (c) of Christ. (20) Thus I make it my ambition to proclaim the good news, (c) not where Christ has already been named, so that I do not build on someone else's foundation.” Footnotes clarify that (b) other ancient authorities read “of the Spirit” or “of the Holy Spirit,” (c) “good news” may also be translated as “gospel,” and (19) identifies Illyricum as a Roman province on the eastern Adriatic Sea. See Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2033.

⁷ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xiii-xiv.

⁸ 2 Corinthians 4:8-9 states: “(8) We are afflicted in every way, but not crushed; perplexed, but not driven to despair; (9) persecuted, but not forsaken; struck down, but not destroyed.” Catalogues of affliction were common in Stoic philosophy, often used to highlight the moral strength of the philosopher. In this passage, however, it is the power of God that sustains the apostle through adversity. See Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2065-2066.

individuals and preached in wider regions than Paul, none have succeeded in planting churches as deeply rooted and self-sustaining as those established by the apostle.

Unlike the protracted, multi-generational efforts often necessary today to create enduring communities of faith, Paul's churches emerged with astonishing speed and stability. This analysis challenges contemporary assumptions about mission work, suggesting that Paul's methods should not be dismissed as outdated relics but rather studied for their potential relevance. Indeed, Allen provocatively argues that advocating for Paul's missionary methods in the modern context might be considered revolutionary, as it runs counter to the dominant view that mission work requires a slow, gradual process marked by extensive training and long-term supervision⁹.

C. Paul's Church Planting: A Timeless Model for Future Generations

Similarly, Roland Allen challenges the widespread assumption that the Apostle Paul's missionary success was solely due to his unique circumstances and extraordinary abilities. Allen argues that the account of Paul's church-planting efforts in the New Testament should not be seen as merely a historical or archaeological curiosity. Rather, it is meant to serve as an enduring guide for Christians today, offering practical instruction on how to carry out the mission of the church (Romans 15:4)¹⁰. Paul's story, Allen asserts, was never intended to be a romanticized legend akin to the tales of El Cid or King Arthur. It was written to illuminate the path for future generations of Christians who seek to spread the Gospel.

Additionally, Allen cites one of the key criticisms is the idea that Paul's methods were bound to his exceptional circumstances—his background, education, divine calling, and the unique social and political environment of his time. Many claim that because Paul was an extraordinary man, his success cannot be replicated in today's world. Allen decisively rejects this view, asserting that Paul's missionary methods were not unique to him alone. They were broadly followed by his disciples and, in fact, have been used by reformers, both religious and secular, across history and cultures. While Paul was certainly a supreme example of the method's power, Allen insists that the method itself is universal, and can be applied in a variety of contexts¹¹.

D. Pride, Prejudice, and the Unmatched Excellence of Paul's Missionary Work

Furthermore, Allen also counters the notion that Paul's advantages—such as his access to the Greek Old Testament and the specific conditions of his age—render his example irrelevant today. In fact, Allen argues, we possess a far greater advantage than Paul did: the printing press

⁹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xiii-xiv.

¹⁰ Romans 15:4, showcases the value of Scripture for instruction, steadfastness, and encouragement, leading to hope. In this letter, Paul claims his divine appointment to spread the gospel to the Gentiles, which explains why he writes to a church he did not personally evangelize. He also refers to the gospel as "of Christ." For further reference, see Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2301-2302.

¹¹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xiii-xv.

and the complete New Testament. These tools make the application of Paul’s methods even more feasible today. Allen’s conclusion is clear: either we must strip Paul of his status as the great missionary, or we must acknowledge that his work holds universal value, transcending his time and circumstances. This challenge invites readers to rethink the relevance of Paul’s methods and to consider how they might be applied in modern missionary work.

Moreover, Allen confronts the prejudice against the Pauline method of missions, a bias that has developed over time due to the misapplication of Paul’s example. Allen argues that this misunderstanding stems from the way Paul’s name has been used to justify poor and ineffective missionary practices. Many missionaries, he notes, have traveled the world “preaching the Word” without laying solid foundations or establishing lasting, informed communities of believers. In their wanderings, they have claimed to follow Paul’s example while failing to reflect the apostle’s intentional, structured approach to church planting¹².

E. Preaching the Gospel and Misinterpreting Paul

Consequently, Allen asserts missionaries often focused on denouncing local religions rather than building the kind of sustainable communities Paul envisioned. Their methods—haphazard and aimless, lacking any clear plan or strategy—are far removed from the strategic, methodical approach Paul employed on his missionary journeys. Allen highlights how these misguided efforts have misrepresented Paul’s work, citing how virtually every form of abuse and inefficiency in mission fields has been erroneously justified by a misreading of Paul’s actions and teachings. This widespread misapplication, according to Allen, is what has led to the prevailing prejudice against the Pauline method, obscuring its true potential for missionary work today. Preaching the gospel is important (1 Corinthians 15:1-4)¹³ and this cannot be overlooked which is the tendency to swing between extremes in how the Pauline method has been understood and applied. Historically, missionary efforts have sometimes been undermined by poorly executed imitations of Paul’s approach, often by ill-prepared or unbalanced individuals, leading to dangerous or ineffective outcomes. In reaction to these failures, there has been a tendency to reject the core principles of Paul’s methodology entirely, overlooking its depth and practicality¹⁴.

F. Misapplication of Paul’s Methods: 4 Common Errors and Practices

¹² Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God’s Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xiv-xv.

¹³ 1 Corinthians 15:1-4 states: “(1) Now I would remind you, brothers and sisters, (a) of the good news (b) that I proclaimed to you, which you in turn received, in which also you stand, (2) through which also you are being saved, if you hold firmly to the message that I proclaimed to you—unless you have come to believe in vain. (3) For I handed on to you as of first importance what I in turn had received: that Christ died for our sins in accordance with the scriptures, (4) and that he was buried, and that he was raised on the third day in accordance with the scriptures.” (a) Greek: *brothers*. (b) Or *gospel*. In verses 15:1-2, Paul underscores that the resurrection faith is integral to the foundation of Christian tradition. In verses 15:3-4, Paul cites an early creed, with the phrase “he was buried” uniquely included, possibly for additional context. See Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 2056.

¹⁴ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God’s Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xv-xvi.

i. Failing to Preach the Gospel and Provide Instruction before Baptism

Allen highlights the common misapplications of Paul's missionary methods, particularly when elements of his approach are adapted within frameworks that contradict his original intent. One such error is the practice of baptizing new converts without providing adequate instruction, which often leads to their eventual abandonment of the faith. Allen emphasizes that Paul himself baptized very few people, choosing instead to focus on preaching the gospel to ensure that new believers received thorough instruction. As Paul writes to the Corinthians, he stresses the importance of preaching over ritual, stating, "I thank God that I baptized none of you, but Crispus and Gaius. For Christ sent me not to baptize, but to preach the gospel, not with wisdom of words, lest the cross of Christ should be made void" (1 Corinthians 1:14, 17)¹⁵. Through this, Allen underscores the critical distinction between Paul's approach to ministry and the misapplications often seen in modern missionary efforts.

A key aspect of Paul's method, as Allen points out, is his emphasis on the proclamation of the gospel over ritual practices like baptism. For Paul, the message of Christ was the foundation of faith, not the outward rituals. This principle serves as a corrective to contemporary practices that place undue emphasis on rituals rather than on the transformative power of the gospel. Allen calls for a return to the core of Paul's methodology, focusing on gospel preaching and discipleship, rather than engaging in practices that may inadvertently weaken the foundation of Christian faith¹⁶.

ii. Discipleship: Equipping Believers for a Life of Service and Righteousness

Allen further critiques the practice of gathering congregations without properly equipping them (not abandoning them to fend for themselves), leading to spiritual regression. In contrast, Paul's model was one of church planting with a strong emphasis on preparation and thorough discipleship. Paul did not leave a church until it was fully equipped for every good work, ensuring that the believers were grounded in Scripture and ready to continue the mission. As Allen notes, Paul's charge to Timothy in (2 Timothy 3:16-17)¹⁷ encapsulates this philosophy: "All scripture is given by inspiration of God and is profitable for doctrine, for reproof, for correction, for instruction in righteousness, that the man of God may be perfect, thoroughly furnished unto all good works". This focus on Scripture as the primary means of instruction and

¹⁵ 1 Corinthians 1:14,17: "(14) I thank God that I baptized none of you except Crispus and Gaius, (17) For Christ did not send me to baptize but to preach the gospel, and not with words of eloquent wisdom, lest the cross of Christ be emptied of its power." The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Cor. 1:14, 17).

¹⁶ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xvi.

¹⁷ 2 Timothy 3:16-17: "(16) All Scripture is breathed out by God and profitable for teaching, for reproof, for correction, and for training in righteousness, (17) that the man of God may be complete, equipped for every good work." The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (2 Tim. 3:16-17).

growth is a central tenet of Paul's missionary strategy, ensuring that new believers are not only reached but equipped for a life of service and righteousness¹⁸.

iii. Failing to Prioritize Elder-Qualified Leaders

In his critique, Allen underscores the stark contrast between modern missionary practices and Paul's approach, particularly regarding the stewardship of mission funds and church leadership. Allen points out that many missionaries have entrusted native helpers with the management of mission funds, only to see these resources misused. However, Paul's approach was different—he did not have funds to entrust to others in the first place. While contemporary efforts have seen missionaries delegate responsibility for funds to native helpers, often resulting in deceit, Paul took a different route. He left the responsibility for financial stewardship within the church itself, empowering local congregations to manage their own resources. As Allen notes, Paul never required a church to render an account of its finances to him. Instead, he instructed the Corinthians, “Now concerning the collection for the saints,... let each one of you set aside in store, as God has prospered him, that there be no collections when I come” (1 Corinthians 16:1-2)¹⁹. This shows Paul's emphasis on personal responsibility and self-sufficiency within the church, rather than imposing external control.

Additionally, Allen critiques the European practice of ordaining uneducated native helpers, which often led to regret. These missionaries broke the natural bonds between the ordained leaders and the congregations they were meant to serve. By imposing foreign systems of church organization, unfamiliar to both the ministers and the people, they created division rather than unity. In contrast, Paul's approach was rooted in the context of the local church. He ordained ministers who were specifically qualified for their roles within their own church communities, focusing on leaders who met the moral and spiritual qualifications outlined in (1 Timothy 3:1-9)²⁰. Paul's emphasis was not on an elaborate, foreign church constitution, but on appointing elder-qualified leaders who were blameless, moral, and upright—leaders who could guide their communities with integrity and faithfulness²¹.

iv. Partial Efforts, Imitations, and Misapplications of the Apostle Paul's Methodologies

Allen astutely asserts that when these false and partial attempts at imitating the Apostle Paul's method have failed, men have declared that the apostolic method was at fault and quite inadequate for the condition and circumstances of present-day missions. The truth is that they have neither understood nor practiced the apostle's method at all. There is yet another, more

¹⁸ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xvi.

¹⁹ 1 Corinthians 16:1-2, states: “(1) Now concerning the collection for the saints: as I directed the churches of Galatia, so you are to do. (2) On the first day of the week, each of you is to put something aside and store it up, as he may prosper, so that there will be no collecting when I come.” *The Holy Bible: English Standard Version*. (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001). 1 Cor. 16:1-2.

²⁰ 1 Timothy 3:1-9 outlines the qualifications for elders, as part of the broader teachings in the Pastoral Epistles. See *The Holy Bible: English Standard Version*. (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001), 1 Tim. 3:1-9.

²¹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xvii.

weight reason for this failure: Paul's method is not in harmony with the modern Western spirit. We modern teachers from the West are by nature and by training persons of restless activity and boundless self-confidence. We tend to assume an attitude of superiority towards all Eastern peoples and point to our material progress as the justification for our attitude. We are accustomed to doing things for ourselves, to finding our own way, to relying upon our own exertions, and we naturally tend to be impatient with others who are less restless and less self-assertive than we are²².

G. The Book's Centers on Paul's Church Planting in Galatia, Macedonia, Achaia, and Asia

Allen makes it clear that his aim is not to delve into the Apostle Paul's character, personal qualifications, or biographical details. Rather, he focuses on a specific period: the establishment of the churches in Galatia, Macedonia, Achaia, and Asia during the ten years of Paul's three missionary journeys. Allen sets out to answer a series of thought-provoking questions that address the underlying principles and methods behind Paul's success in building these early Christian communities. The first question Allen raises concerns the geographical and social context of the cities where Paul planted churches. Did Paul deliberately choose strategic locations, and were there particular advantages in the cities he selected? He explores whether Paul's success was influenced by the social, moral, or religious conditions of the provinces, which may have been vastly different from modern contexts. Next, Allen examines the distinctive aspects of Paul's approach to preaching the gospel. He discusses whether Paul's use of miracles, his financial practices, and the substance of his preaching contributed to the effectiveness of his ministry. This leads to further consideration of Paul's methods in training and teaching new converts, as well as the peculiar virtues in his approach to discipleship²³.

H. Part I – Strategic Points, Class, and Moral and Social Condition

i. Strategic Points

1. Strategic Points. Did Paul deliberately select certain strategic points at which to establish his churches?
2. Existence of a Peculiar Class. Was his success due to the existence of some peculiar class of people to which he made a special appeal?
3. Social, Moral, and Religious Condition. Did the social, moral, or religious condition of the provinces differ so much from anything known in modern times, as to render futile any comparison between his work and ours?

²² Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xviii.

²³ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xx.

Roland Allen addresses the question of whether the Apostle Paul deliberately selected strategic points for the establishment of churches during his missionary journeys. Allen examines the idea of whether Paul's success can be attributed to a peculiar class of people or if the social, moral, and religious conditions of the provinces he visited were so unique that comparisons to modern missionary work would be irrelevant. While Allen contends that there is insufficient evidence to prove that Paul intentionally planned his journeys, the notion of strategic planning still arises from the language in Acts. In Acts 13:2²⁴, the Holy Spirit directs Barnabas and Saul to embark on "the work" to which they are called, and in Acts 14:26²⁵, they return to Antioch²⁶, reporting on the "work" they had completed.

Although Allen acknowledges that these references suggest Paul's missionary activities involved some level of preparation, he ultimately concedes that Paul's plans were often redirected by the Holy Spirit (Acts 19:21)²⁷. This insight suggests a balance between divine guidance and strategic planning, with Paul's journeys likely involving a mix of both. As Allen himself concludes on pages 3-5, the truth behind Paul's missionary methods likely lies in the synergy between the Holy Spirit's leading and Paul's practical, strategic decisions. This nuanced view challenges the idea that Paul's mission was purely spontaneous or entirely planned, pointing instead to a dynamic interplay of divine direction and thoughtful planning²⁸.

Allen provides several points to ponder: (1) Just as Paul refrained from preaching in his native regions and passed through large towns in Antiochus' territory without stopping to preach, he similarly bypassed smaller provincial towns like Mithia or Vasada within the Roman province. Instead, he chose to preach in places like Lystra and Derbe—military posts with a significant Roman presence. Professor Ramsay has shown that in the Book of Acts, there appears to be a deliberate contrast between how local authorities treated Paul and how Roman officials responded to him.

The narrative seems to highlight the Romans as protectors of the apostle, in contrast to the persecution he faced from the Jewish authorities. (2) The centers where Paul established his churches were all hubs of Greek civilization. Even in Lystra, half of the inscriptions discovered are in Greek, while the other half are in Latin. Throughout the Roman Empire, Roman governance was closely intertwined with Greek education. This educational system provided Paul with a common medium of communication, enabling him to effectively engage with diverse

²⁴ Acts 13:2 states: "While they were worshipping the Lord and fasting, the Holy Spirit said, 'Set apart for me Barnabas and Saul for the work to which I have called them.'" The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version* (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001), Acts 13:2.

²⁵ Acts 14:26 states: "And from there they sailed to Antioch, where they had been commended to the grace of God for the work that they had fulfilled." The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version* (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001), Acts 14:26.

²⁶ "Antioch," *Encyclopedia Britannica*, August 16, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Antioch-modern-and-ancient-city-south-central-Turkey>.

²⁷ Acts 19:21 states: "Now after these events Paul resolved in the Spirit to pass through Macedonia and Achaia and go to Jerusalem, saying, 'After I have been there, I must also see Rome.'" The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version* (Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001), Acts 19:21.

²⁸ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 3-5.

audiences across the empire. (3) Nearly all the places where Paul established churches were centers of Jewish influence. (4) Paul established his churches at places that were centers of the world's commerce²⁹.

ii. Class

In contemporary discussions about evangelism, there is a prevailing focus on targeting specific classes of people within a given society. This approach is often seen as a means of maximizing outreach and fostering significant influence. Roland Allen illustrates this concept with a compelling example from the history of the Natural Foot Society in China, where a carefully directed appeal to a particular class led to remarkable outcomes³⁰. He draws parallels to the apostolic ministry by examining key passages such as Acts 18:4-6 and 2 Corinthians 11:22-23, where Paul's approach to different audiences is highlighted³¹. Additionally, Allen references 2 Corinthians 11:23-27 and Acts 13:45 to further demonstrate how Paul navigated his missionary efforts, often facing challenges in his engagement with various social groups³². Furthermore, Allen explores Paul's remarks in Romans 1:16 and Romans 9:2-4, emphasizing the apostle's inclusive vision for the Gospel that transcended social barriers³³. Through these passages, Allen underscores the importance of understanding the role of class in evangelistic efforts and how Paul's ministry reflects both strategic and inclusive outreach.

iii. Moral and Social Condition

The locations where Paul established his churches were hubs of Roman and Greek civilization. When we refer to Graeco-Roman civilization, we often envision the profound teachings of renowned philosophers, imagining a society deeply shaped by their ideas. However, within the empire, there was no unified standard of civilization. The major cities were home to a diverse array of religions and a wide spectrum of peoples, ranging from highly cultured individuals to those living in more primitive conditions. Points to ponder: (1) The first is the prevalence of belief in demons. (2) The work of Paul in the four provinces is the moral character of the religious rites. (3) But in addition to these factors, there were two evils, the likes of which are not now found throughout the world – slavery and the amphitheater. (4) Finally, there was slavery, which was very different in Paul's days from any slavery known to us – and not for the better.

²⁹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 3-10.

³⁰ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 13.

³¹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 15; The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Acts 18:4-6, 2 Cor. 11:22-23).

³² Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 16; The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (2 Cor. 11:23-27, Acts 13:45).

³³ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 17; The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Rom. 1:16, 9:2-4).

On pages 25-26, he documents, “The first is the widespread belief in demons: ‘In times of distress, heathenism naturally turned to devil worship.’ ‘Not merely idolatry, but every aspect of life was governed by them. They sat on thrones, hovered around cradles, and the earth was literally a hell.’ ‘The whole world lies in the *Evil One*.’”³⁴ He points out that this belief was not confined to barbarians or Phrygians but was also held by Romans, Greeks, and Jews. It was not just the uneducated, but also the most cultured, who were convinced of the universal power of demons, much like the Chinese or the *Gonds* today.³⁵ The consequences of this belief, then as now, were physical and psychiatric diseases, cruelty, bondage, and vice. Men like *Pliny the Elder*³⁶, who argued that it was the height of irreverence to attribute adultery and strife to the gods and to believe in deities associated with theft and crime, still believed in the most horrific forms of magic. Human sacrifice was not uncommon, and belief in witchcraft was widespread. Educated men believed that enemies could secretly influence their lives through incantations. Plutarch, a learned and virtuous man, was serious when discussing rites associated with ill-omened and evil days, which included devouring raw flesh, mutilating bodies, fasting, beating the breast, making obscene cries at altars, and engaging in frenzied behavior. While *Plutarch*³⁷ did not believe these rites were meant to worship gods, he thought they were meant to appease or ward off evil demons. The magical incantations that have been found recently can be traced back to these early practices. The formulas likely contributed to the magical books, worth fifty thousand pieces of silver that were publicly burned in *Ephesus*³⁸ under Paul’s influence³⁹.

Allen inscribes on page 27, “In heathen lands, it may still be wiser to consistently preach the supremacy of Christ over all things spiritual and material rather than deny or mock the belief in spirits. Some missionaries understand, and it would benefit others to realize, that it is far easier for a person to hide their belief in demons than to rid themselves of it. By denying their existence or ridiculing those who believe in them, we do not aid our converts in overcoming these beliefs but merely cause them to conceal their fears from us. By preaching the supremacy of Christ, however, we offer a true remedy: we point them to a real Savior who assists them in their darkest moments⁴⁰.”

Furthermore, Allen records on page 29, “It is upon these two conditions, superstition and uncleanness, that nearly all our arguments for our modern methods of conducting missionary

³⁴ Roland Allen references this passage but notes the source as uncertain, citing it as (14).

³⁵ “Gonds,” *EveryCulture*, accessed November 29, 2024, www.everyculture.com/wc/Germany-to-Jamaica/Gonds.html.

³⁶ “Pliny the Elder,” *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, accessed November 29, 2024, www.britannica.com/biography/Pliny-the-Elder.

³⁷ “Plutarch,” *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, accessed November 29, 2024, www.britannica.com/biography/Plutarch.

³⁸ “Ephesus,” *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, accessed November 29, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Ephesus>.

³⁹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 25-26.

⁴⁰ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 27.

work in heathen lands today are based. We should remind ourselves that whatever may be the merits of Paul’s methods, they do not rest upon social religious conditions superior to those under which most of our modern missions are conducted.”⁴¹

Additionally, Allen notes on page 31, “These spectacles had two highly destructive effects: (1) they reinforced the division of humanity into two classes—men with rights and men without rights, which was the fundamental curse of slavery; and (2) the excitement they generated made all other, more reasonable forms of entertainment seem dull in comparison. In particular, their impact on the theater was disastrous. With the intense excitement of the circus and the arena, the stage could only attract audiences through degenerate means—rough humor and vulgarity. Nothing was too crude, nothing too obscene, to be shown in the theater; nothing was too sacred to be mocked. The myths of the gods often served as the basis for the most grotesque and degrading performances.”⁴²

III. Review of the Second-Half of *Missionary Methods*

The latter sections of Roland Allen’s *Missionary Methods* spans from pages 39-201 (Sections II-V), the author delves into critical aspects of missionary practice. However, the treatment of these topics often leaves much to be desired in terms of depth and intellectual engagement. Part II begins with a discussion on *Miracles*, where Allen addresses the role of supernatural acts in the apostolic mission. He emphasizes the centrality of the Word of God over miraculous signs, yet his treatment of the issue seems somewhat dismissive of the ongoing role of miraculous gifts in modern missions. While his point about the sufficiency of preaching is valid, the lack of exploration into the complexities of spiritual gifts today weakens his argument. The section on *Finance* is similarly pragmatic, advocating for a reliance on local support and self-sustaining mission strategies. While Allen’s insights on financial independence are grounded in a clear sense of stewardship, the topic feels overly simplistic, especially in a global context where financial dynamics in missions are far more complex.⁴³

The section on *The Substance of Paul’s Preaching* is perhaps the most valuable in this part of the book. Allen insightfully highlights that Paul’s message was rooted in the gospel’s power to transform lives, emphasizing salvation through Christ as the core of his ministry. However, Allen’s tendency to oversimplify modern views of evangelism detracts from his analysis, particularly in failing to address the full spectrum of theological approaches to preaching in today’s missions.⁴⁴

⁴¹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God’s Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 29-31.

⁴² Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God’s Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 31-39.

⁴³ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God’s Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 39-67.

⁴⁴ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God’s Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 67-88.

Part III, covering *The Teaching and the Training of Candidates for Membership and Ministry*, reveals Allen's focus on the role of the local church in training new leaders. While Allen rightly stresses the importance of establishing strong, biblically grounded leadership, the section could benefit from a more detailed exploration of contemporary challenges in leadership development and the diversity of approaches seen in mission fields today.⁴⁵

In Part IV, *Authority and Discipline* and *Unity* are discussed in the context of church organization and mission. Allen argues that the church's authority should be rooted in scripture and that unity among believers is paramount. His arguments here are solid, but the application to modern missions feels overly rigid. The dynamics of church authority and unity today often involve more complex issues such as denominationalism, theological differences, and cultural tensions, which Allen doesn't fully address.⁴⁶

Finally, Part V, with sections on *Principles and Spirit, Application*, and *A Present-Day Contrast*, attempts to connect Paul's methods to contemporary mission work. However, Allen's application of Paul's methods to today's world feels dated, especially given the significant shifts in missionary practice and the challenges of globalized missions in the modern era. The *Present-Day Contrast* section, while well-intended, fails to address the evolving landscape of missions in a nuanced way, offering more of a general critique than a comprehensive comparison.⁴⁷

Overall, while parts of these sections provide useful insights, Allen's treatment of the topics remains overly idealistic and lacks the depth required to fully engage with the complexities of modern missionary work. His reliance on idealized readings of Paul's ministry, without sufficiently addressing the dynamic challenges of contemporary missions, leaves the work feeling incomplete. Additionally, Allen's focus on theoretical frameworks often overlooks the practical realities faced by missionaries on the ground, such as cultural barriers, political instability, and the spiritual warfare that frequently accompanies cross-cultural ministry. His tendency to present Paul's ministry as a "one-size-fits-all" model fails to account for the diverse contexts in which today's missionaries operate, diminishing the applicability of his conclusions. As a result, while Allen's ideas may inspire, they fall short of offering tangible solutions or strategies for addressing the pressing issues in global mission work today.

⁴⁵ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 89-120.

⁴⁶ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 121-156.

⁴⁷ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 157-201.

IV. Critique and Analysis of *Missionary Methods*: Part I

A. Refuting *Missionary Methods*: Fervor & Expansion and R.C. Sproul

In his analysis of the Apostle Paul’s missionary success, Roland Allen claims that Paul’s rapid and widespread establishment of churches across the Roman Empire was unparalleled, with no comparable growth seen in later centuries. However, this assertion overlooks several key factors and is ultimately flawed. R.C. Sproul (c. 1939 – 2017 AD), a renowned theologian, challenges Allen’s thesis and view in his book *Everyone is a Theologian*, where he warns against building a fragmented theology or “atomism”⁴⁸ by focusing exclusively on one biblical figure, such as Paul, or on just the New Testament or Old Testament. According to Sproul, a holistic approach is necessary to understand the broader narrative of God’s complete work. This critique highlights a key problem with Allen’s thesis and argument: by isolating Paul’s achievements, one risks overlooking the broader historical and theological context in which those achievements occurred.⁴⁹

B. Refuting *Missionary Methods*: Fervor & Expansion - Justin Martyr, Emperor Diocletian, and Tertullian

Justin Martyr’s reflections on early Christian martyrdom and persecution provide a compelling alternative explanation for the rapid spread of Christianity⁵⁰. In *Church History in Plain Language* by Bruce L. Shelley he further highlights other factors contributing to the growth of the Church, such as Christian love, mercy, and courtesy towards enemies, citing Tertullian’s famous statement: “See how these Christians love one another.”⁵¹ Shelley notes that persecution, rather than hindering the Gospel, often fueled its expansion. The willingness of early Christians to endure brutal deaths—whether torn apart by wild animals or executed publicly—served as a powerful testimony to the truth of their faith. To those who witnessed these acts of unwavering courage, the steadfastness of the martyrs made the Christian message appear undeniably true, prompting further conversions. Additionally, Shelley discusses the pivotal role of martyrdom, particularly during the reign of Emperor Diocletian (c. 244 – 311 AD), and ruled from (284 – 305 AD) in facilitating the spread of Christianity⁵². This suggests that the expansion of Christianity cannot be attributed solely to Paul’s unique missionary methods, but also to the powerful witness of Christian martyrdom⁵³.

⁴⁸ “Atomism,” *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, last modified November 14, 2023, accessed November 29, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/atomism>.

⁴⁹ R.C. Sproul addresses a significant issue in seminaries today: the method of biblical theology referred to as “atomism,” where individual parts of Scripture are treated as isolated units. He notes that some scholars, for instance, may focus solely on Paul, leading to a narrow understanding of the Bible. Sproul cautions that this approach jeopardizes the unity of Scripture and fosters a fragmented theology by disregarding its overarching framework. See R.C. Sproul, *Everyone is a Theologian: An Introduction to Systematic Theology* (Sanford, FL: Ligonier Ministries, 2014), 10–12.

⁵⁰ Bruce L. Shelley, *Church History in Plain Language*, 5th ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2021), 42-75.

⁵¹ Bruce L. Shelley, *Church History in Plain Language*, 5th ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2021), 45.

⁵² Bruce L. Shelley, *Church History in Plain Language*, 5th ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2021), 122-125.

⁵³ Bruce L. Shelley, *Church History in Plain Language*, 5th ed. (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2021), 42-125.

V. Critique and Analysis of *Missionary Methods*: Part II

A. God's Providence: Roman Empire's Infrastructure, Council of Nicaea, and Constantine

Furthermore, scholars such as Dr. Kenneth Calvert of Hillsdale College argued that the Roman Empire's infrastructure played a significant role in the expansion of Christianity. Dr. Calvert highlights how the Roman Empire's roads, common language (Koine Greek), and political unity provided an ideal environment (or vehicle) for the rapid dissemination of the Gospel. In this light, the success of Paul's missionary efforts can be seen as part of a broader historical moment, shaped by God's providential use of the Roman Empire. Dr. Calvert also points to the influence of Constantine and the Council of Nicaea in 325 AD as pivotal factors in the spread of Christianity. Constantine's conversion and subsequent legal recognition of Christianity transformed the faith from a persecuted sect to a legitimate and powerful movement within the empire. The Council of Nicaea further consolidated Christian doctrine, providing theological unity that supported the expansion of the faith. Dr. Calvert reiterates the point by stating "the Apostle Paul was not the only Apostle and that we need to look at the Bible as a whole (See the EWTN interview at 23:50-57 mark)."⁵⁴ Together, these perspectives challenge Roland Allen's narrow view of Paul's missionary success, offering a more nuanced understanding of the factors that contributed to the spread of Christianity. The interplay of divine providence, the infrastructure of the Roman Empire, Christian love, mercy, and courtesy, the witness of martyrs, and historical events like Constantine's conversion and the Council of Nicaea (325 AD) all played crucial roles in the growth of the early Church. Thus, the argument that Paul's success was extraordinary and unmatched by later missionary efforts fails to account for the multifaceted ways in which the Gospel spread.

B. Refuting *Missionary Methods*: Absolutism and Pragmatism

Roland Allen's assertion about Paul's theology and missionary methodology should caution a person to not fall into the trap of "*absolutism*"⁵⁵ in missionary practices. According to Britannica, *absolutism* in this context implies the belief that Paul's methods and theology is the only legitimate model to be used in missionary work. This viewpoint maintains that any deviation from the practices Paul demonstrated in the New Testament is either ineffective or invalid. Proponents of this absolute perspective argue that the fervor, strategies, and approaches used by Paul should be universally applied in all missionary efforts, often dismissing alternative methods as insufficient or erroneous. However, such a rigid interpretation of Paul's mission may overlook the evolving nature of missionary work, which must adapt to different cultural and historical contexts to be effective and relevant. Allen's thesis and view in his book *Missionary*

⁵⁴ Dr. Kenneth Calvert, professor at Hillsdale College, discusses the Apostle Paul and notes that he was not the only apostle in an interview with EWTN on December 21, 2020. See "12/21/20 Dr. Kenneth Calvert," published December 21, 2020, EWTN, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A_DzMZCWcBk.

⁵⁵ "Absolutism," *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, last modified November 14, 2023, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/absolutism-political-system>.

Methods comes across as having pragmatic characteristics (See *Pragmatism*)⁵⁶.

C. Refuting Missionary Methods: Reductionism

Moreover, Allen would probably be best characterized as a *reductionist* at least in the philosophical sense (See *Reductionism*).⁵⁷ This is due to Allen's tendency to simplify the complexities of missionary work by emphasizing a core set of principles Allen believes were exemplified in the Apostle Paul's methods. Allen's *reductionism*, however, is not about dismissing complexity altogether, but rather about focusing on what he viewed as the most fundamental, biblically-prescribed aspects of missionary efforts. Some of his views reduce complex aspects of missionary work to certain core principles taught by the Apostle Paul. Allen advocates for a simple, biblically grounded approach to missions, emphasizing the role of the Holy Spirit and the importance of local leadership in establishing churches. His thoughts are often interpreted as reducing the complex strategies and structures of missionary work to what he considered to be the New Testament pattern for missionary work. This is why some may perceive Allen as a reductionist. This does not imply that the teachings of the Apostle Paul are without value or that they lack lessons worth embracing. The concern lies in failing to integrate Paul's teachings and methodologies with those of the other Apostles and the broader teachings of the Bible, rather than treating them as a cohesive whole.

D. Examining Allen's Interpretation of Paul's Methodology

Allen offers a profound exploration of the Apostle Paul's unparalleled success in establishing the early Christian church. Recognizing the ongoing challenge of building thriving, self-sustaining congregations, Allen emphasizes the importance of revisiting Paul's methods. Rather than delving into doctrinal debates, this work focuses on Paul's practical strategies, which allowed the church to flourish, resolve internal conflicts, and withstand external pressures. Allen makes it clear that his book is not a treatise on Paul's theology but an investigation into his methodology. He acknowledges the contentious nature of doctrinal interpretation, particularly on issues like baptism and church organization. For instance, while it is widely accepted that Paul instructed converts on baptism, opinions on its theological significance differ. Allen employs language consistent with his own denominational perspective but invites readers of all traditions to engage with Paul's methods, setting aside doctrinal disputes in favor of practical analysis. This ecumenical approach is one of the book's strengths.

Allen transcends denominational boundaries, arguing that Paul's strategies for church planting, discipleship, and leadership development are universally applicable. He highlights Paul's success in creating communities that could operate independently and adapt to challenges, providing a model that is both timeless and relevant for modern ministry. By focusing on the facts of Paul's work rather than divisive theological details, Allen ensures that his insights are accessible to a wide audience. He urges readers to consider how Paul's emphasis on equipping churches for autonomy and growth can inform contemporary practices. For Allen, the Apostle's

⁵⁶ "Pragmatism," *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, Accessed November 29, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/pragmatism-philosophy>.

⁵⁷ "Reductionism," *Encyclopaedia Britannica*. Accessed November 29, 2024. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/reductionism>.

achievements serve as a reminder of the importance of practical, Spirit-led strategies in fostering healthy and resilient congregations. Ultimately, *Paul's Methodology* is a call to action for church leaders, missionaries, and believers seeking to revitalize their ministries. Allen's thoughtful analysis provides valuable tools for addressing the challenges of modern church life while drawing inspiration from Paul's enduring legacy. This book is not just a study of history but a guide for shaping the future of the church⁵⁸.

E. Scriptures that Support the Apostle Paul's Methodologies

(2 Corinthians 10:5)⁵⁹ aligns with Allen's argument, stating, "We destroy arguments and every lofty opinion raised against the knowledge of God, and take every thought captive to obey Christ." This verse challenges reliance on human constructs and highlights the need for a faith rooted in obedience to Christ rather than dependence on elaborate church systems or rigid moral codes. Similarly, (John 4:23-24)⁶⁰ reinforces Allen's emphasis on authenticity in worship, focusing on spiritual truth rather than external forms or rituals. These verses call believers to prioritize their relationship with God over man-made systems or machinery, underscoring the heart of Allen's critique of modern missionary practices. We often expect converts to adopt not only the core tenets of the gospel but also the cultural and traditional practices that accompany them. This approach contrasts sharply with Paul's methods, which were driven by a different spirit—one that favored persuasion over authority. Paul rejected elaborate systems of religious ceremony, instead focusing on foundational principles and placing unwavering trust in the power of the Holy Spirit to guide believers (John 16:13)⁶¹ in developing their own expressions of faith. Consequently, Paul's methods, rooted in freedom and spiritual authenticity, were as unsettling to the Jewish Christians of his time as they are to modern proponents of rigid structures. The resemblance of Paul's approach to an unstructured "no method" style only amplifies the skepticism of those who prioritize order and control.

F. The Key to the Apostle Paul's Success

Furthermore, Allen also explores Paul's management of the organized churches. How did Paul handle issues of discipline and maintain unity among the believers? By investigating these aspects, Allen uncovers the methods Paul employed to ensure that his churches remained strong, cohesive, and self-sustaining. Finally, Allen draws readers to certain core principles that seem to underpin Paul's methodology, which he believes hold the key to the apostle's success. The author thoughtfully suggests how these apostolic methods could be applied in contemporary mission work. While Allen refrains from citing specific examples from modern mission fields, his general observations about current trends and tendencies in missionary work provide a helpful framework for understanding how Paul's methods might still be relevant today. Overall,

⁵⁸ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), ixx-xx.

⁵⁹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (2 Cor. 10:5).

⁶⁰ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (John 4:23-24).

⁶¹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (John 16:13).

Paul's Methodology offers a compelling exploration of the practical aspects of Paul's missionary strategy. It serves as a valuable resource for anyone seeking to understand how Paul's example can inform modern ministry and mission work. Allen's clear and focused approach ensures that the book remains both insightful and applicable, highlighting timeless principles for effective gospel proclamation and church building⁶².

VI. Critique and Analysis of *Missionary Methods*: Part III

A. Deliver Us From Evil: A Refutation of Roland Allen's View on Demons

i. Framing the Debate on Demons and Understanding the Greek

Roland Allen suggests that the widespread belief in demons, though pervasive across many cultures, should not be the primary focus of missionary work. He argues that, rather than engaging directly with these spiritual beliefs, missionaries should preach the supremacy of Christ over all things spiritual and material. While Allen's insights about the complexities of indigenous spiritual beliefs and the need for compassionate engagement are valuable, his conclusion about the nonexistence of demons and the simplicity of preaching Christ as the answer does not sufficiently account for the spiritual realities that missionaries often encounter.⁶³ Derek Prince (c. 1915 – 2003 AD) a respected authority on spiritual warfare and Greek scholar, offers a counterpoint to Allen's thesis by emphasizing the actual existence of demons and the necessity of addressing them directly in ministry, deliverance, and missionary work.

The Greek word *daimonion* (“δαίμόνιον”)⁶⁴ is typically translated as “demon,” “unclean spirit,” or “evil spirit” in the New Testament, and is Strong's #1140. The Greek phrase *pneuma akatharton* (“πνεῦμα ἀκάθαρτον”), meaning “unclean spirit,” appears in at least five significant passages in the New Testament. The term “unclean” (*akatharton*) is used 32 times throughout the text. A notable example is Matthew 12:43 (NRSV), which states: “When the unclean spirit has gone out of a person, it wanders through waterless places, looking for a resting place, but it finds none.”⁶⁵ Derek Prince explains that the important distinction between the Greek words *daimon* and *daimonion* is often obscured because both terms are typically translated into English as “demon.” Throughout his book, he maintains that whenever it is crucial to preserve this distinction, he will use the Greek words transliterated into English and italicized—*daimon* and

⁶² Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), xx-xxi.

⁶³ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 22-27.

⁶⁴ The Greek word *daimonion* (δαίμόνιον), occurring 63 times in the New Testament, refers to “a heathen god,” “deity,” “demon,” or “evil spirit” (Strong's #1140). The Greek phrase *pneuma akatharton* (πνεῦμα ἀκάθαρτον), meaning “unclean spirit,” appears in several meaningful New Testament passages, including Matthew 12:43, Mark 1:23, Mark 3:30, Luke 4:33, and Luke 11:24. The word *akatharton* (ἀκάθαρτον), which means “unclean,” appears 32 times in the New Testament. The Strong's numbers for “spirit” and “unclean” are 4151 and 169, respectively. See William D. Mounce, *Mounce's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1075-1115.

⁶⁵ Matthew 12:43: The reference to “waterless regions” reflects the ancient belief that demons dwelt in desolate places such as deserts (see Matt. 4:1; Tobit 8:3). For further details, see Michael D. Coogan, ed., *The New Oxford Annotated Bible with Apocrypha: New Revised Standard Version*, 5th ed. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2018), 1800.

daimonion. The plural will be formed by adding an "s," though this is not the proper Greek pluralization. Prince further clarifies that the original King James Version (KJV) of the Bible often translates *daimonion* as "devil," which has caused significant confusion. The English word "devil" actually comes from the Greek word *diabolos*, which is unrelated to *daimonion*.

Diabolos (διάβολος)⁶⁶ means "slanderer" or "traitor" or "the devil" and is used in the New Testament almost exclusively as a title for Satan, appearing in the singular form and is Strong's # 1228. While there are many demons, there is only one devil.⁶⁷

ii. Allen's View of Demons and Demonology: Viewed as Superstition or Fantasy

Allen's treatment of demonology suggests that the belief in demons is merely a cultural construct or a form of superstition, arguing that in times of distress, "heathenism naturally turned to devil worship," and that even educated individuals, like Pliny the Elder and Plutarch, accepted magic and witchcraft as part of their spiritual worldview. According to Allen, missionaries should not ridicule or deny the existence of spirits but instead preach the supremacy of Christ to offer a remedy for fear and spiritual bondage. However, Allen fails to fully address the reality of spiritual forces that often manifest in a tangible, oppressive way in the lives of individuals. While preaching Christ's supremacy is undeniably important, Derek Prince's writings on spiritual warfare highlight that the existence of demons is a reality that cannot be dismissed as superstition.⁶⁸

Derek Prince, in his book *They Shall Expel Demons*, argues that the Bible is clear in its depiction of demons as real, active agents of evil that work to oppress, deceive, and destroy human lives. He notes that throughout Scripture, Jesus and His followers routinely confronted demons and cast them out as part of their ministry. Prince asserts that to ignore or downplay the presence of demons in contemporary ministry is to neglect an essential aspect of spiritual warfare. He writes, "Jesus not only preached the kingdom of God but also demonstrated the power of the kingdom over the kingdom of darkness." This power, Prince argues, is available to all believers who engage in the spiritual battle against evil forces. Far from simply preaching

⁶⁶ The Greek word *diabolos* (διάβολος) (Strong's #1228) is commonly translated as "the devil" and means "slanderer" or "traitor." It is used in the New Testament almost exclusively as a title for Satan, the primary adversary of God and humanity. *Diabolos* refers to one who falsely accuses, misrepresents, or maliciously speaks against someone. In contrast to *daimonion* (δαμόνιον) (Strong's #1140), which denotes a demon or evil spirit, *diabolos* specifically refers to Satan, emphasizing his role as the ultimate accuser and adversary. In all but three occurrences in the New Testament, *diabolos* appears in the singular form, highlighting the uniqueness of Satan as the singular "devil." A notable example of *diabolos* is found in John 6:70: "Jesus answered them, 'Did I not choose you, the twelve? Yet one of you is a devil.'" While *diabolos* is used 37 times in the New Testament, it is not always used to refer to Satan. For instance, it also appears in 1 Timothy 3:11: "Women likewise must be serious, not slanderers, but temperate, faithful in all things." See William D. Mounce, *Mounce's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1119.

⁶⁷ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 14-15.

⁶⁸ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 23-27.

Christ's supremacy in an abstract sense, Prince advocates for a hands-on approach in which believers actively confront and cast out demons in the name of Jesus.⁶⁹

In contrast to Allen's more passive approach, which calls for preaching the supremacy of Christ without directly addressing the demonic, Prince emphasizes that engaging with spiritual forces is essential for effective ministry, particularly in cultures where demon worship and spiritual oppression are prevalent. The belief in demons, as Allen acknowledges, is not limited to uneducated or primitive cultures but is still a prominent feature of many modern spiritual systems. Whether through direct encounters with demonic forces or through the destructive consequences of demonic influence (such as physical and psychiatric diseases), the reality of spiritual oppression is evident.⁷⁰

iii. Understanding the Concept of Casting Out, Driving Out, and Expelling in Greek

In his book, Prince argues that the most accurate way to describe the interaction between demons, people, and the Bible is by using the term "demonized." While the Greek verb (*ekballō*)⁷¹ is traditionally translated as "to drive out" or "to cast out" in the King James Version, Prince prefers Weymouth's translation, "expel," as it conveys a more familiar, everyday action. Throughout his work, Prince uses these terms—"cast out," "drive out," and "expel"—interchangeably.⁷²

iv. A Tale of Self-Deliverance in *They Shall Expel Demons*

On pages 32–33 of his book, Derek Prince recounts an experience of self-deliverance from the spirit of heaviness or despair. He describes reading the opening verses of Isaiah 61, which highlight the supernatural work of the Holy Spirit in affirming the message of the Gospel—passages that Jesus Himself applied to His ministry in the synagogue at Nazareth (see Luke 4:16–21)⁷³. As he reached the words in Isaiah 61:3b (NIV): "... and a garment of praise instead of a spirit of despair. They will be called oaks of righteousness, a planting of the Lord for the display of his splendor,"⁷⁴ he found himself unable to continue reading. It felt as though the phrase "spirit of heaviness" had been underlined by an unseen hand. This brought to mind a term he had once heard but not fully understood: *familiar spirit*. He wondered if it referred to a kind

⁶⁹ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 17-25.

⁷⁰ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 23-30.

⁷¹ The Greek verb ἐκβάλλω (*ekballō*), meaning "to cast out" or "to drive out," is Strong's #1544 and appears 81 times in the New Testament. In Matthew 8:16, this verb refers to the action of Jesus casting out spirits with a word. This demonstrates the authority of Christ in expelling demons. For further details, see William D. Mounce, *Mounce's Complete Expository Dictionary of Old and New Testament Words* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2006), 1134.

⁷² Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 8–9.

⁷³ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Luke 4:16-21).

⁷⁴ The Holy Bible: *New International Version* (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 2011), Isaiah 61:3.

of evil power that attached itself to families, passing from one generation to the next.⁷⁵

Derek Prince reflects on his father, who had achieved the rank of Colonel in the Army. Despite his accomplishments, a persistent shadow seemed to loom over his father's life. Upon recognizing that this might be a generational issue, the Holy Spirit brought a verse to Derek Prince's attention: Joel 2:32 KJV, which declares, "And it shall come to pass, that whosoever shall call on the name of the Lord shall be delivered."⁷⁶ From his studies in Hebrew, Derek Prince understood that this verb also carries the meaning "to save" or "to rescue." Determined to apply this biblical promise, he decided to act on the prompting of the Holy Spirit.

Prince offered a simple yet heartfelt prayer that went something like this: "Lord, You've revealed to me that I have been oppressed by a spirit of heaviness, but Your Word promises that whoever calls on Your name shall be delivered. So, I am calling on You now to deliver me, in the name of Jesus!"⁷⁷

While Allen's argument that missionaries should not ridicule or dismiss these beliefs is valid, he overlooks the practical necessity of addressing the demonic realm directly. Preaching Christ's supremacy over spiritual forces is essential, but it must be accompanied by active deliverance ministry to break the power of demons in the lives of individuals. Derek Prince's work offers a more comprehensive approach that not only acknowledges the reality of spiritual forces but also provides practical tools for confronting them through prayer, fasting, and the use of the authority given to believers in Christ.⁷⁸

v. Contemporary Examples of Preaching on Demons

On November 22, 2024, evangelical pastor Mark Driscoll preached about the presence of demons within the church, sharing his insights on their manifestation among some of his parishioners. Driscoll, a former Reformed pastor and now leader of Trinity Church in Scottsdale, Arizona, discussed how certain individuals in his congregation were experiencing demonic manifestations. In response, Kap Chatfield created a reaction video, sharing the story of a man from his own church who was delivered during a prayer meeting. This man, who wishes to remain anonymous, had been struggling with depression and suicidal thoughts but found freedom and healing through deliverance. Chatfield draws parallels (8:08 mark) between this

⁷⁵ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 32-33.

⁷⁶ The Holy Bible: *King James Version*. (Nashville: Thomas Nelson, 2020), Joel 2:32.

⁷⁷ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 33-35.

⁷⁸ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 26-29.

story and the account in (Acts 16:16-32)⁷⁹, where the Apostle Paul delivers a slave girl from a spirit of divination.⁸⁰

vi. Judas' Manifest Moment and The Betrayal of Jesus

In his teaching, Pastor Driscoll explains that a “manifest moment” occurs when a demon is revealed, typically through the host losing control, allowing the demon to momentarily take full control of the individual. He uses Judas as an example, pointing out that his betrayal of Jesus with a kiss marked the moment when the demon within him fully seized control. Pastor Driscoll emphasizes the gravity of this moment (starting at the 14:57 mark)⁸¹, by saying, “literally this is the kiss of death. He literally murders his God. This was Judas’s manifest moment.” This moment is captured in (Luke 22:48): “but Jesus said to him, ‘Judas, would you betray the Son of Man with a kiss?’”⁸² Driscoll goes on to encourage believers to avoid bitterness when encountering someone in a manifest moment, cautioning that such negativity can open the door for Satan to influence one’s life as well (15:42 mark)⁸³.

Allen’s perspective, though valuable in its call for respect and compassion toward those with spiritual beliefs, underestimates the importance of spiritual authority and deliverance in the life of the believer. As Derek Prince asserts, “The only way to deal with demons is to confront them directly with the power of Christ.” In mission fields where belief in spirits and demonic influence is widespread, this confrontational approach is necessary—not merely to preach the supremacy of Christ, but to demonstrate His power over every spiritual stronghold (See Letter of Paul to the Colossians).⁸⁴

In conclusion, while Roland Allen offers useful insights into the approach missionaries should take toward spiritual beliefs, his view that demons are a mere cultural construct and should be ignored in favor of preaching Christ’s supremacy fails to acknowledge the reality of demonic oppression. Derek Prince’s teachings provide a more thorough understanding of spiritual warfare, urging missionaries to not only preach Christ’s supremacy but also engage in active deliverance ministry to help people break free from the spiritual bondage of demons. Therefore, a more holistic approach, one that combines the proclamation of Christ’s victory with direct confrontation of demonic forces, is essential for effective ministry in spiritually oppressed

⁷⁹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Acts 16:16-32).

⁸⁰ Kap Chatfield, *Mark Driscoll Exposes Demons In Church | Kap Reacts*, YouTube video, 8:08, published November 26, 2024, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eLL0zzpq2zA>.

⁸¹ Kap Chatfield, *Mark Driscoll Exposes Demons In Church | Kap Reacts*, YouTube video, 14:57, published November 26, 2024, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eLL0zzpq2zA>.

⁸² The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Luke 22:48).

⁸³ Kap Chatfield, *Mark Driscoll Exposes Demons In Church | Kap Reacts*, YouTube video, 15:42, published November 26, 2024, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=eLL0zzpq2zA>.

⁸⁴ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 21-28; T. Editors of Encyclopaedia Britannica, "Letter of Paul to the Colossians," *Encyclopaedia Britannica*, August 18, 2020, <https://www.britannica.com/topic/The-Letter-of-Paul-to-the-Colossians>.

cultures.

Derek Prince, a renowned evangelist, missionary, Bible teacher, and Greek scholar, extensively addresses demonic activity and the ministry of deliverance in his book *They Shall Expel Demons*. In the introduction (p. 8), Prince writes: “Nearly two thousand years ago Jesus came to the help of suffering humanity, working miracles by healing the sick and casting out demons. Throughout the three and a half years of His earthly ministry, this never changed. In the intervening centuries Christian men and women have been called from time to time with miraculous ministries to help the sick and afflicted.”⁸⁵

Prince recounts a pivotal moment in 1963 that led him into the deliverance ministry. During a church service, a member of his congregation emitted a *blood-curdling scream and collapsed before the pulpit*. Reflecting on this event, Prince shares: “That experience in 1963 propelled me into intensive study of the ministry of Jesus. Mark begins his record of the public ministry of Jesus, I discovered, with an incident in which a demon challenged Him as He was teaching in a synagogue in Galilee. This encounter spread His fame immediately throughout the whole of Galilee (See Mark 1:21-28).”⁸⁶ This profound experience and subsequent study deepened Prince’s commitment to understanding and practicing the ministry of deliverance as modeled by Jesus.⁸⁷

vii. Conclusion

A. Powerful Testimony - Spiritual Warfare from Dr. John Mulinde

One of the most powerful sermons I have heard on demons and spiritual warfare was delivered by Ugandan Pastor Dr. John Mulinde. The sermon titled “A Call to Repentance Through John Mulinde's Testimony – Jesus is Coming Back,” the sermon was published on YouTube by Truthhurtsrealtalk on November 27, 2013. In this impactful message, Pastor Mulinde shares personal testimony and biblical insights on spiritual warfare, emphasizing the urgent call for repentance in light of Christ’s return.”⁸⁸ The bulk of the sermon explores the following Scripture passages:

i. New Testament: 1 Corinthians 6, John 12, Matthew 3, 5, and 7, Mark 10, Luke 12, Hebrews 1, 2, and 12, James 4, *Romans 1, 2, 11, and 12*, Revelation 3, 16, and 22.

ii. Old Testament: Proverbs 3 and 16, *Jeremiah 6–7*, Isaiah 40 and 55, Exodus 19, Joshua 3, Numbers 11 and 32, Psalms 27, 30, 46, and 149.

⁸⁵ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 8–9.

⁸⁶ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 8–10. The Holy Bible: English Standard Version. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Mark 1:21-28).

⁸⁷ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 9-16.

⁸⁸ Dr. John Mulinde, *A Call to Repentance Through John Mulinde's Testimony – Jesus Is Coming Back*, Truthhurtsrealtalk, YouTube video, 1:36:59, November 27, 2013, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=it5jcFWc1P8&t=2318s>.

During the sermon Pastor Mulinde discusses a visitation from the Lord Jesus Christ through a vision and revelation. During the sermon he outlines how he and a group of elders and deacons traveled with him and through the power of Jesus Christ and they were used by God to deliver a powerful warlock to Jesus Christ. The warlock was a high ranking warlock in Satan's army.⁸⁹ Once the warlock was converted to Christianity the whole village came back to the Lord Jesus Christ and hundreds of villagers converted to Christianity. When Pastor Mulinde received a visitation from the Lord Jesus Christ the Lord told him if I had come from my bride I would not have taken you. He said outwardly you were professing the right things, but your heart was filthy and he shared in the sermon and testimony that the Lord Jesus revealed his heart to him. This was the passages from Romans 2:11 NIV: "For God does not show favoritism."⁹⁰

This revelation and vision led Pastor Mulinde to a profound moment of repentance. Upon realizing the condition of his heart, despite his outward professing, he was deeply convicted. The Lord's words revealed the need for true inward purity and repentance (Psalm 51:10 and Ezekiel 36:26)⁹¹. This powerful encounter prompted Pastor Mulinde to seek genuine reconciliation with God, humbling himself before the Lord and acknowledging the areas of his life that required transformation. The verse that became Mulinde's overture and thesis was Isaiah 61:3a NIV: "...the oil of joy instead of mourning..."⁹² Through this experience, he not only experienced personal renewal but was also moved to share the importance of true repentance with others in his congregation and beyond. On his website he writes: "All spiritual warfare is about destiny."⁹³

B. Healing and Deliverance was a Large Portion of Jesus' Ministry

Lastly, the notion that demons and deliverance play no role in missionary work is simply unfounded. In fact, nearly 30% of Jesus' three-and-a-half-year ministry was focused on healing and deliverance. There are around 70 recorded healing events and at least 25 instances of deliverance in the Gospels, resulting in a rough estimate of about 100 significant acts of healing and deliverance. This number may even be higher, as some passages describe Jesus simultaneously healing and casting out demons, while others summarize His ministry more broadly. Therefore, it is reasonable to conservatively estimate that 30%, and possibly as much as 50%, of Jesus' ministry involved some form of healing or deliverance. Additionally, Jesus often does not distinguish between deliverance and healing, and in many cases, the two are treated as the same. Furthermore, deliverance and healing were integral to the gospel message that Jesus proclaimed, emphasizing both spiritual and physical restoration. In many instances, Jesus' acts of deliverance served as signs of the Kingdom of God breaking into the present world. This

⁸⁹ Truthhurtsrealtalk, *A Call to Repentance Through John Mulinde's Testimony - Jesus Is Coming Back*, YouTube video, 17:14, published November 27, 2013, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=it5jcFWc1P8&t=2318s>.

⁹⁰ The Holy Bible: New International Version (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 2011), Romans 2:11.

⁹¹ The Holy Bible: English Standard Version. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Psalm 51:10, Ezekiel 36:26).

⁹² The Holy Bible: New International Version (Grand Rapids: Zondervan, 2011), Isaiah 61:3.

⁹³ Dr. John Mulinde, "Teaching Library," *Dr. John Mulinde Ministries*, accessed November 30, 2024, <https://www.drjohnmulinde.com/teachinglibrary>.

underscores the relevance of spiritual warfare in missionary efforts today, demonstrating that confronting spiritual oppression is not only biblical but also a necessary aspect of advancing the Kingdom in the world.⁹⁴

B. Refuting *Missionary Methods*: Model Journey and Strategic Planning

Roland Allen's work on missionary methods has long been lauded for its insightful analysis of the Apostle Paul's unparalleled success in church planting. However, his claim that Paul's missionary journeys lacked deliberate planning warrants closer examination. While Allen's emphasis on the spontaneity of Paul's efforts provides an inspiring framework for contemporary missions, his dismissal of strategic intent in Paul's methods is open to critique. Insights from Hans Conzelmann in the *Hermeneia Commentary on Acts*, as well as from scholars Dibelius and Bultmann, present a compelling counterargument grounded in Luke's account of Paul's journeys. Hans Conzelmann's interpretation of (Acts 13:1-4)⁹⁵ provides significant evidence of a structured and deliberate approach in Paul's missionary work.⁹⁶

Conzelmann argues that Luke's narrative portrays Paul's first journey as a "model journey," emphasizing Antioch (See Britannica: Antioch)⁹⁷ as both the starting point and final destination. This assertion runs counter to the claims made by Allen. This dual role highlights Antioch's strategic importance as a center for spreading Christianity among the Gentiles. The framing also underscores Luke's theological intent to portray the unity of the church, composed of Jews and Gentiles, with Antioch serving as a critical hub subordinate only to the dogmatic authority of Jerusalem. This deliberate emphasis suggests that Paul's movements were more than circumstantial; they reflected a clear understanding of the pivotal role of certain locations in the early church's expansion. Further support for the argument of deliberate planning comes from Dibelius and Bultmann, who propose that Luke's narrative incorporates an underlying "itinerary."⁹⁸ Dibelius suggests that Luke built upon a pre-existing framework of Paul's movements, enriching it with detailed accounts of key stops along the way.⁹⁹ Similarly, Bultmann's analysis reinforces the idea of a purposeful structure, noting that Luke's presentation of the journey reflects strategic design rather than random progression. Together, these scholars

⁹⁴ Derek Prince, *They Shall Expel Demons* (Bloomington, MN: Chosen Books, 2006), 63-85.

⁹⁵ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Acts 13:1-4).

⁹⁶ Hans Conzelmann, *Acts of the Apostles*, *Hermeneia: A Critical and Historical Commentary on the Bible*, ed. Eldon Jay Epp and Christopher R. Matthews (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1987), 98-99.

⁹⁷ "Antioch," *Encyclopedia Britannica*, August 16, 2024, <https://www.britannica.com/place/Antioch-modern-and-ancient-city-south-central-Turkey>.

⁹⁸ Rudolf Bultmann, "Zur Frage nach den Quellen der Apostelgeschichte," in *New Testament Essays: Studies in Memory of T. W. Manson 1893-1958*, ed. A. J. B. Higgins (Manchester: Manchester University Press, 1959), 423.

⁹⁹ Martin Dibelius, *Studies in the Acts of the Apostles* (New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1956), 41-91.

highlight the organized nature of Paul's activities as presented in Acts, challenging Allen's portrayal of them as largely spontaneous.¹⁰⁰

Luke's depiction of Paul's missionary work provides additional evidence against Allen's claim. The repeated references to Antioch as a base for operations, the deliberate choice of mission fields, and the gradual but intentional shift in leadership dynamics between Barnabas and Paul all point to a thoughtful strategy in Paul's approach. Conzelmann's observation that the first journey serves as a model for subsequent missions further solidifies the argument for intentional planning. By portraying Paul's work as deliberate and methodical, Luke presents a narrative that aligns closely with the structured approach advocated by modern mission strategists. While Allen's work rightly emphasizes the adaptability and Spirit-led nature of Paul's missions, his claim that they lacked planning oversimplifies the nuanced portrait found in Luke's account. Conzelmann, Dibelius, and Bultmann collectively demonstrate that Paul's efforts were underpinned by a level of intentionality and strategy that Allen's framework does not adequately address. As such, contemporary readers would benefit from a more balanced view that incorporates both the spontaneity and the strategic brilliance of Paul's missionary endeavors¹⁰¹.

C. Refuting *Missionary Methods*: Biblical Foundations for Guidance and Strategy

Examining Allen's claims alongside the Apostle Paul's missionary efforts reveals a balance between divine guidance and human intentionality, underscoring that Paul's work was both inspired and methodically planned. This duality is supported by several key Scriptures. Proverbs 16:9¹⁰² reminds us, "The heart of man plans his way, but the Lord establishes his steps," highlighting the interplay between human initiative and God's sovereignty. Proverbs 15:22¹⁰³ underscores the value of strategic collaboration, stating, "Without counsel plans fail, but with many advisers they succeed." This verse affirms the importance of seeking wisdom and input when crafting plans, a principle likely reflected in Paul's approach. Psalm 1:1¹⁰⁴ further emphasizes intentionality, declaring, "Blessed is the man who walks not in the counsel of the wicked, nor stands in the way of sinners, nor sits in the seat of scoffers." This passage suggests a deliberate alignment with godly wisdom and purpose in one's decisions. Isaiah 30:21¹⁰⁵ illustrates how divine guidance works alongside human planning: "And your ears shall hear a word behind you, saying, 'This is the way, walk in it,' when you turn to the right or when you turn to the left." This imagery reinforces the notion that Paul's journeys were shaped by a dynamic partnership between strategic forethought and God's direction. Together, these

¹⁰⁰ Hans Conzelmann, *Acts of the Apostles*, Hermeneia: A Critical and Historical Commentary on the Bible, ed. Eldon Jay Epp and Christopher R. Matthews (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1987), 98-100.

¹⁰¹ Hans Conzelmann, *Acts of the Apostles*, Hermeneia: A Critical and Historical Commentary on the Bible, ed. Eldon Jay Epp and Christopher R. Matthews (Philadelphia: Fortress Press, 1987), 98-99.

¹⁰² The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Proverbs 16:9).

¹⁰³ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Proverbs 15:22).

¹⁰⁴ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Psalm 1:1).

¹⁰⁵ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Isaiah 30:21).

Scriptures provide a robust foundation for understanding Paul’s missionary work as a thoughtful, intentional endeavor, blending faith and foresight to achieve remarkable outcomes.

D. Refuting *Missionary Methods*: The Importance of Cities & Strategic Planning

Michael Gorman points out in his discussion of “Paul’s Cities and the Importance of Cities,” Paul’s ministry was not a random series of encounters, but a methodical approach centered around key urban hubs. Gorman highlights that Paul spent much of his time in cities, recognizing that these urban centers were not only populous but also hubs for diverse philosophical and religious thought, providing fertile ground for spreading the Gospel.¹⁰⁶

The cities Paul targeted, such as Corinth, Philippi, and Ephesus, were often either longstanding historical centers or strategically rebounded as colonies that served as regional religious and commercial capitals. These cities were well-connected by roads and shipping routes, facilitating the rapid exchange of ideas and beliefs, much like modern-day transportation networks. The deliberate choice of cities with significant trade routes and harbors, like Corinth, underscores the strategic nature of Paul’s evangelism. These cities, with their bustling populations and cultural exchanges, provided ideal environments for spreading the Christian message. The expansion of the Gospel through such urban centers reflects a carefully considered strategy, demonstrating that Paul’s missionary efforts were not haphazard but intentionally directed toward places with maximum potential for impact¹⁰⁷.

In light of this, Gorman’s observations reinforce the argument against Allen’s claim that Paul’s evangelism lacked strategic planning. Rather, Paul’s ministry was marked by purposeful, calculated decisions aimed at reaching urban populations, facilitating the spread of Christianity through well-established, interconnected cities in the Roman Empire. These efforts show that Paul’s missionary journeys were not simply guided by divine inspiration, but were also shaped by a clear and effective strategic vision.¹⁰⁸

VII. Applying Paul’s Missionary Methods to the Modern Church

A. How the Apostle Paul would Confront Sin in the Church

If a church were engaged in such practices as idolatry, sexual immorality, self-promotion, occult practices, worship of money, backstabbing, and neglecting widows, the poor, and stewardship of resources, Paul would likely take a multifaceted approach rooted in both correction and restoration. Based on his missionary methods and teachings throughout his letters, here's how Paul might address these issues:

¹⁰⁶ Michael Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to Paul & His Letters* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2017), 42-43.

¹⁰⁷ Michael Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to Paul & His Letters* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2017), 42-44.

¹⁰⁸ Michael Gorman, *Apostle of the Crucified Lord: A Theological Introduction to Paul & His Letters* (Grand Rapids: Wm. B. Eerdmans Publishing Co., 2017), 43-49.

1. Confront Sin with Clear Teaching and Exhortation

Paul did not shy away from addressing sin head-on in the churches he planted. He consistently rebuked sinful behavior with clarity and authority, especially when it undermined the integrity of the church and its witness to the world. For example:

A. Idolatry & Occult Practices:

Paul would likely call for a complete renouncement of idolatry and occult practices. In (Acts 19:18-19)¹⁰⁹, after many people in Ephesus repented of their former occult practices, they burned their magical books as a public declaration of their new allegiance to Christ. He would likely teach the supremacy of Christ over all false gods and spiritual forces (1 Corinthians 8:4-6).

B. Sexual Immorality:

Paul strongly condemned sexual immorality (1 Corinthians 5:1-13, 6:9-20)¹¹⁰, urging the church to maintain purity and honor God with their bodies. He would call for repentance, discipline (if needed), and a return to holiness (Ephesians 5:3-5)¹¹¹.

C. Worship of Money (Greed):

In (1 Timothy 6:9-10)¹¹², Paul warned that the love of money is the root of all evil, and he urged the church to pursue godliness with contentment. He would likely teach against materialism and challenge the church to adopt a radical generosity and trust in God's provision (2 Corinthians 9:6-8)¹¹³.

2. Emphasize the Gospel and Repentance

Central to Paul's methods was always the gospel. He would continually point the church back to the gospel of grace and emphasize the need for repentance and faith. He would urge the church to remember the forgiveness and transformation available in Christ (1 Corinthians 6:9-11)¹¹⁴. In his letters, Paul stresses the power of the Holy Spirit to transform lives, so he would call for a fresh understanding and dependence on the Spirit's work to produce true holiness in the

¹⁰⁹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Acts 19:18-19).

¹¹⁰ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Cor. 5:1-13,6:9-20).

¹¹¹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Eph. 5:3-5).

¹¹² The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Tim. 6:9-19).

¹¹³ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (2 Cor. 9:6-8).

¹¹⁴ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Cor. 6:9-11).

lives of the members (Romans 8:13, Galatians 5:16-25)¹¹⁵.

3. Reinforce Biblical Community and Accountability

Paul's method emphasized a strong, accountable community of believers. In his letters, he called for mutual support and admonition within the body of Christ (Galatians 6:1-2, Colossians 3:16)¹¹⁶. Paul would advocate for restoring relationships within the church through loving confrontation and gentle restoration, ensuring that the body of Christ is united and works together to bear one another's burdens.

4. Practical Care for Widows and the Poor

Addressing the neglect of widows and the poor would be a major point for Paul, as he was passionate about care for the marginalized and the needy (1 Timothy 5:3-16, James 1:27)¹¹⁷. He would likely stress the importance of practical love and mercy ministries. He would remind the church of Christ's call to care for the least of these (Matthew 25:31-46)¹¹⁸. Paul's own missionary efforts included the collection for the poor in Jerusalem (Romans 15:25-27, 2 Corinthians 8-9)¹¹⁹, so he would likely teach the church to be sacrificial in their giving and to steward their finances well, ensuring that resources are used for the Kingdom, not self-indulgence.

5. Call to Selflessness and Humility

Paul consistently emphasized humility and service over self-promotion (Philippians 2:3-4, 1 Corinthians 13:4-7)¹²⁰. In a church caught up in self-promotion and backstabbing, Paul would call the members to embrace a Christ-like attitude of sacrificial love and unity (Ephesians 4:1-3)¹²¹. He would urge them to put the needs of others above their own and to foster an environment where love, honor, and respect are the governing principles of interaction.

6. Discipline and Restoration

Paul was not afraid to call for church discipline when necessary. He would likely establish a process of accountability for those living in unrepentant sin, urging church leaders to take the

¹¹⁵ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Rom. 8:13, Gal. 5:16-25).

¹¹⁶ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Gal. 6:1-2, Col. 3:16).

¹¹⁷ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Tim. 5:3-16, James 1:27).

¹¹⁸ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Matt. 25:31-46).

¹¹⁹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Rom 15:25-26, 2 Cor. 8-9).

¹²⁰ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Phil. 2:3-4, 1 Cor. 13:4-7).

¹²¹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Eph. 4:1-3).

necessary steps to restore people to a right relationship with God and with one another. However, his goal was always restoration, not condemnation (Galatians 6:1, 2 Corinthians 2:5-11)¹²².

7. Teach About the Church's Purpose and Mission

Finally, Paul would refocus the church on its mission to be a light to the world, pointing them to their role in the Kingdom of God. He would remind them that the church is a community of redeemed people, set apart to proclaim the gospel and to live lives that reflect God's holiness and love (1 Peter 2:9-12)¹²³. Paul would call them to abandon their selfish, sinful ways and embrace the missional purpose of the church.

Summary:

Paul's approach to addressing serious issues like idolatry, sexual immorality, greed, neglecting the poor, and interpersonal conflicts would be one of clear teaching, correction, restoration, and a return to the foundational truths of the gospel. He would emphasize the power of the Holy Spirit to transform lives, the importance of church discipline and accountability, and the need for practical love and care for the vulnerable. Ultimately, Paul would point the church back to its true calling: to live as a holy, humble, and loving community that reflects the character of Christ and engages in the mission of God in the world.

B. What was the Substance of Paul's Preaching and How does it Apply to the Church Today?

The Apostle Paul is often considered one of the most influential figures in the New Testament and Christian history. His letters and missionary journeys shaped much of early Christian thought, doctrine, and practice. The substance of Paul's preaching can be distilled into key themes such as the proclamation of Jesus Christ as Lord and Savior, justification by faith, the power of the Holy Spirit, the unity of the Church, and the call to holy living. These themes not only defined Paul's ministry in the first century but continue to be relevant for the Church today.

1. The Centrality of Christ in Paul's Preaching

At the heart of Paul's message is the proclamation of Jesus Christ as the crucified and resurrected Savior. Paul emphasizes that salvation is found in Christ alone, a message that he frequently underscores in his letters. In 1 Corinthians 2:2, Paul writes, "For I decided to know nothing among you except Jesus Christ and Christ crucified."¹²⁴ This statement reveals the centrality of Christ's death and resurrection in Paul's preaching. Paul consistently preached the

¹²² The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Gal. 6:1-2, 2 Cor. 2:5-11).

¹²³ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Peter 2:9-12).

¹²⁴ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Cor. 2:2).

gospel of Christ's death, burial, and resurrection as the foundation of the Christian faith (1 Corinthians 15:3-4)¹²⁵.

This emphasis on Christ's work is foundational for the Church today. The Church must continue to uphold Christ as the center of its proclamation, for without Christ's sacrificial death and victorious resurrection, there is no hope for salvation. As Paul points out in 1 Timothy 1:15, "The saying is trustworthy and deserving of full acceptance, that Christ Jesus came into the world to save sinners, of whom I am the foremost."¹²⁶ This truth should remain the primary message the Church shares, reminding believers and non-believers alike of God's redemptive plan through Jesus Christ.

2. Justification by Faith

Another key element of Paul's preaching is the doctrine of justification by faith. Paul emphasizes that human beings are justified, or declared righteous, before God not by works of the law but by faith in Jesus Christ. This is most clearly articulated in Romans 3:28, where Paul writes, "For we hold that one is justified by faith apart from works of the law."¹²⁷ Paul continually refuted the idea that salvation could be earned through human effort or adherence to the Mosaic Law. Instead, he proclaimed that faith in Jesus Christ alone is the means by which sinners are made right with God.

The doctrine of justification by faith is crucial for the Church today, especially in an era where many still try to earn God's favor through good deeds or religious rituals. The Church must be a place where the message of grace is central, where people are taught that salvation is a gift from God, not something that can be achieved by human merit. In Ephesians 2:8-9, Paul reinforces this teaching, saying, "For by grace you have been saved through faith. And this is not your own doing; it is the gift of God, not a result of works, so that no one may boast."¹²⁸ This doctrine is liberating, for it frees the believer from the burden of self-effort and points them to the sufficiency of Christ's work on their behalf.

3. The Power of the Holy Spirit

Paul's preaching also emphasizes the transformative power of the Holy Spirit. The Holy Spirit is not only the agent of salvation but also the one who empowers Christians to live out their faith. In Romans 8:11, Paul writes, "If the Spirit of him who raised Jesus from the dead dwells in you, he who raised Christ Jesus from the dead will also give life to your mortal bodies

¹²⁵ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Cor. 15:3-4).

¹²⁶ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Tim. 1:15).

¹²⁷ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Rom. 3:28).

¹²⁸ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Eph. 2:8-9).

through his Spirit who dwells in you.”¹²⁹ The presence of the Holy Spirit in the life of the believer is central to Paul’s message, as it is the Spirit who enables Christians to live righteous lives, bear fruit, and carry out the mission of the Church.

For the Church today, the power of the Holy Spirit remains vital. Without the Holy Spirit’s presence and empowerment, the Church is powerless to fulfill its mission. The Church must continually rely on the Holy Spirit for guidance, conviction, and strength. In Galatians 5:16, Paul urges believers to “walk by the Spirit,”¹³⁰ recognizing that only through the Spirit can they overcome the flesh and live according to God’s will. The Spirit also gifts believers for ministry, as Paul writes in 1 Corinthians 12:4-7, emphasizing that “to each is given the manifestation of the Spirit for the common good.”¹³¹

4. The Unity of the Church

Paul’s preaching consistently emphasized the importance of unity within the body of Christ. In Ephesians 4:3-6, Paul urges believers to “eagerly maintain the unity of the Spirit in the bond of peace.”¹³² He speaks of one body, one Spirit, one hope, one Lord, one faith, one baptism, and one God and Father of all, highlighting the unity that should characterize the Church. This unity is not based on human efforts but is created and sustained by the Holy Spirit.

In the modern Church, unity remains a vital issue. The Church today, like in Paul’s time, faces division along various lines—doctrinal, denominational, cultural, and racial. However, Paul’s teaching calls the Church to work toward unity, recognizing that believers, regardless of background, are part of the same body of Christ. As Paul writes in Galatians 3:28, “There is neither Jew nor Greek, there is neither slave nor free, there is no male and female, for you are all one in Christ Jesus.”¹³³ This truth challenges the Church today to break down walls of division and to promote unity in Christ.

5. Call to Holy Living

Lastly, Paul’s preaching always carried a strong call to holy living. He consistently encouraged believers to live in a manner worthy of the gospel. In 1 Thessalonians 4:3-7, Paul writes, “For this is the will of God, your sanctification: that you abstain from sexual immorality; that each one of you know how to control his own body in holiness and honor, not in the passion

¹²⁹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Rom. 8:11).

¹³⁰ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Gal. 5:16).

¹³¹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Cor. 12:4-7).

¹³² The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Eph. 4:3-6).

¹³³ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Gal. 3:28).

of lust like the Gentiles who do not know God.”¹³⁴ Paul stressed that Christians are called to be distinct from the world, living according to God’s standards of holiness.

For the Church today, this call to holy living is as important as ever. In a culture that often promotes moral relativism and self-indulgence, the Church must continue to teach and model holiness, not as a means of salvation, but as the fruit of salvation. As Paul urges in Romans 12:1-2, believers are called to present their bodies as “a living sacrifice, holy and acceptable to God, which is your spiritual worship,”¹³⁵ and to be transformed by the renewal of their minds.

Conclusion

The substance of Paul’s preaching—Christ’s work of salvation, justification by faith, the power of the Holy Spirit, the unity of the Church, and the call to holy living—remains profoundly relevant for the Church today. These core themes are not only central to the Christian faith but also essential for the Church’s mission in the world. Just as Paul’s preaching transformed the early Church, it continues to serve as a guide for how the Church should live and proclaim the gospel today. Through faithful preaching of the same truths, the Church can continue to grow in grace and truth, empowered by the Holy Spirit to fulfill its calling in the world.

VIII. Conclusion

A. Conclusion and Critique of *Missionary Methods*

In conclusion, while Roland Allen (c. 1868–1947 AD) and his book *Missionary Methods* provide some valuable insights into the early Church’s missionary efforts, the work ultimately feels more like an exercise in defending a singular thesis than an objective analysis of Paul’s strategies. Allen’s tendency to make bold claims about the distinctiveness of Paul’s methods—only to contradict or temper these claims later—diminishes the strength and coherence of his arguments. Moreover, his efforts to silence criticism through additional works further obscure the clarity of his message. For readers seeking a comprehensive and balanced examination of the Apostle Paul’s approach to mission, this book falls well short. Moreover, while it may be considered provocative, it lacks the consistency and scholarly depth expected from a theologian, particularly one with cessationist leanings from the early twentieth century.

Additionally, many scholars, including Dr. Kenneth Calvert, Derek Prince, Garry Friesen, Dr. John Mulinde, Mark Driscoll, Kap Chatfield, Michael Gorman, R.C. Sproul, and Hans Conzelmann and others, caution against the tendency to focus solely on Paul’s theology and methodologies without considering the broader context of the Bible. They argue that a comprehensive understanding of Paul’s writings requires integrating them within the larger narrative of Scripture. Dr. Calvert, for instance, emphasizes the importance of viewing Paul’s letters as part of the whole biblical canon, rather than isolating them from other biblical texts. Similarly, Gorman highlights the need to read Paul within the narrative of God’s redemptive

¹³⁴ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Thess. 4:3-7).

¹³⁵ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Rom. 12:1-2).

work as revealed throughout Scripture, not as a standalone voice. R.C. Sproul and Hans Conzelmann also advocate for a holistic approach to biblical interpretation, one that recognizes the unity and continuity of the entire biblical message. These scholars assert that a theologically sound and accurate understanding of Paul's letters can only be achieved by recognizing them as part of the larger biblical story, which provides necessary context for interpreting Paul's thoughts and teachings.

B. Conclusion and Critique of *Missionary Methods*

While Roland Allen did not explicitly advocate for or against *cessationism*¹³⁶, his views on the Holy Spirit's role in the church's mission did not prioritize miraculous gifts as essential or normative for missionary work. Instead, Allen focused on the authority of Scripture, the importance of the church's witness, and the Holy Spirit's role in empowering evangelists. He placed emphasis on the local church's outreach, viewing ordinary means of grace—such as preaching, prayer, and the sacraments—as central to mission work, rather than expecting miraculous signs and wonders. This practical approach to missions may lead some to interpret him as implicitly supporting the cessation of certain gifts, especially those common in the apostolic era. However, he did not formally argue for cessationism in the same way that Reformed theology typically does. His views on the Holy Spirit were pragmatic, emphasizing the effectiveness of the church in its mission rather than focusing on supernatural manifestations.

In contrast, *Decision Making & The Will of God* by Garry Friesen highlights the critical role of the Holy Spirit in guiding believers' decisions, offering a biblical framework for how the Spirit leads choices in alignment with God's will¹³⁷. I agree with Allen that the gospel should be the central focus of the church's mission. However, it is also important to recognize the Bible's comprehensive teaching on spiritual warfare (Ephesians 6:11-12)¹³⁸. Allen's perspective, which seems to downplay spiritual opposition, leaves believers vulnerable to deception. As Paul warns in 2 Timothy 3:5¹³⁹, the denial of truth is not merely a social or cultural issue but a spiritual one, influenced by the unseen powers of evil. Our adversary, the devil, roams like a roaring lion (1 Peter 5:8)¹⁴⁰, and there is ongoing spiritual opposition that we must resist. By underplaying these forces, as Allen does on pages 23-27, there is a risk of neglecting the importance of standing firm against the deception and attacks of the enemy¹⁴¹.

¹³⁶ Matt Marino. "Cessationism." *Reformed Classicalist*. Accessed November 30, 2024. <https://www.reformedclassicalist.com/home/cessationism>.

¹³⁷ Garry Friesen with J. Robin Maxon, *Decision Making & the Will of God: A Biblical Alternative to the Traditional View* (Portland, OR: Multnomah Press, 1982), 29-37.

¹³⁸ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (Eph. 6:11-12).

¹³⁹ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (2 Tim. 3:5).

¹⁴⁰ The Holy Bible: *English Standard Version*. Wheaton, IL: Crossway, 2001. (1 Peter 5:8).

¹⁴¹ Roland Allen, *Missionary Methods: God's Plan for Missions According to Paul*, updated ed. (Abbotsford, WI: Aneko Press, Life Sentence Publishing, 2017), 23-27.

C. Conclusion and Critique of *Missionary Methods*

Overall, Roland Allen's book often feels like he constructs straw man arguments to easily dismantle, which weakens his thesis. He simplifies or exaggerates opposing views to make his own points seem more convincing, avoiding deeper engagement with the complexities of missionary work. While his approach provides intellectual satisfaction by addressing opposing views quickly, it lacks the depth necessary for thorough exploration. This one-sided critique prevents balanced dialogue and leaves his arguments feeling superficial. Additionally, his weak citations and obscure references raise concerns about the credibility of his claims. Allen's approach offers intellectual satisfaction by quickly addressing opposing views, but it lacks the depth required for a thorough exploration of the topic. Instead of fostering balanced dialogue, he oversimplifies issues with one-sided critiques, dismissing alternative perspectives in missionary theory and practice. This makes it hard to engage critically with his work, especially for those seeking a comprehensive analysis. His arguments, while potentially valid, come across as superficial, lacking the intellectual rigor to persuade skeptics. Additionally, his weak citations further undermine the credibility of his claims. Lastly, Allen makes several citations where the referenced works are unfamiliar or obscure altogether, which raises concerns about their reliability or accessibility. Overall, Allen makes a compelling case for learning from the Apostle Paul's methodology and his gospel teachings but his implementation and supports are flawed.

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